

Talent Management and Mentoring of Excellent Students

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Abstract

Academies are globally competing on the quality of staff and students. These values have established global markets for talents. One of the critical nominators I have found during my extensive private academic mentoring is that academic mentoring is done voluntarily in addition to the curriculum and students have varying degrees of access to it. This problem is even more significant considering excellent students who will need not only one but several or tens of additional scientific and philosophical mentors to make improvements at an accelerated rate. No university is really prepared for this part. All this effort is extra-curricular, and the workload can be counted in thousands of hours. The only easing thing is that these hours are shared between scientific communities and experts from multiple universities. In the end, resourcing this issue would be the responsibility of ministries of education in each country. It is a responsibility to recognise how much effort it will take for the scientific community to replenish new generations of excellent scientists and philosophers with new ones without lowering the general quality.

The general problem is that most of the authorities do not recognise this mentoring work, and most universities think that surpassing courses and titles with excellent performance indicating grades would be enough. But it is not enough by half. With enough guidance, these people could make scientific peer-reviewed papers during their master's thesis. With enough mentoring, gifted doctoral students could achieve meta-analysis, theory articles and other hard feats even for professional scientists. Thus, I want to raise attention to this potential because the university system doesn't in a direct way support these kinds of operations. However, with or without this support, the scientific community must continually develop a new generation of scientists and a new generation of professors with excellent capabilities. This task is also cumulatively more difficult to solve by each generation of scientists. Considering global trends of quality competition in many fields, this will be one of the critical areas where larger improvements can be made.

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